

A Proof of Goldbach Conjecture by Using Goldbach Partition Model Table and Sieve Functions

Tae Beom Lee

join360@naver.com

Abstract

Goldbach's Conjecture(GC) states that any even integer ≥ 4 can be represented by the sum of two prime numbers. This was conjectured by Christian Goldbach in 1742 and still remains unproved. In this thesis we proved GC by introducing Goldbach Partition Model Table(GPMT) and Sieve Functions(SFs). GPMT is a 2-dimensional table of all possible pair of two numbers $(x, 2n - x)$, whose sum can be any even number $2n$. To functionally treat the sieve of Eratosthenes we devised SFs that have sinusoidal symmetry and period properties. By using GPMT and the graphs of SFs, we could induce a condition set that must be satisfied if GC is false. And by introducing complementary function concept, we proved that the condition set can not be satisfied.

1. Introduction

GC [1][2] states that any even number ≥ 4 is the sum of two prime numbers, like $22 = 3 + 19 = 5 + 17 = 11 + 11$, $38 = 7 + 31 = 19 + 19$. The conjecture has been shown to hold for all integers less than 4×10^{18} [3], but remains unproved despite various efforts [4][5][6]. First, let's define a basic terminology of GC.

Definition 1.1. Goldbach Partition(GP) : A pair of two prime numbers (p, q) that satisfies $2n = p + q$, $n = 2, 3, 4, \dots$

In this thesis, we devised Goldbach Partition Model Table(GPMT) and Eratosthenes Sieve Functions(SFs). GPMT is a 2-dimensional arrangement of all possible GPs for a specific even number $2n$, and SFs are functional representation of the sieve of Eratosthenes. By using GPMT and SFs, we could visually understand the symmetry and period properties of GC, from which we induced a condition set that must be satisfied if GC is false. And by introducing complementary function concept, we proved the condition set can not be satisfied.

2. Goldbach Partition Model Table(GPMT)

Lemma 2.1. Possible GPs for $2n \geq 4$ have the form $(x, 2n - x)$, $x = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Proof. GP is the sum of two primes $p + q = 2n$, so, $q = 2n - p$, i.e., $(p, q) = (p, 2n - p)$. So, possible GPs have the form $(x, 2n - x)$. ■

Definition 2.2. Goldbach Partition Model Table(GPMT) : A table with all possible GPs of the form $(x, 2n - x)$, as in Table 1, and has the following properties.

Table 1 shows an example GPMT for $n = 25, 2n = 50$. Numbers 1, 2, ..., 49 are arranged downward and upward. Apparently, $x + (2n - x) = 2n$, so, all possible GPs reside in the table. Numbers marked as red are prime numbers. Detail explanations are as follows.

Table 1. Example GPMT for $n = 25$.

x	2n - x	Forward sieve seed			Reverse sieve seed		
		3	5	7	3	5	7
1	49						7u
2	48				16u		
3	47	1d					
4	46						
5	45		1d		15u	9u	
6	44	2d					
7	43			1d			
8	42				14u		6u
9	41	3d					
10	40		2d			8u	
11	39				13u		
12	38	4d					
13	37						
14	36			2d	12u		
15	35	5d	3d			7u	5u
16	34						
17	33				11u		
18	32	6d					
19	31						
20	30		4d		10u	6u	
21	29	7d		3d			
22	28						4u
23	27				9u		
24	26	8d					
25	25		5d			5u	

• **Horizontal arrangement.**

- **x** : Forward(increasing) sequence from 1 to n which is the smaller(down, denoted by d) number of a possible GP pair $(x, 2n - x)$.
- **2n - x** : Reverse(decreasing) sequence from $2n - 1$ to n which is the larger(up, denoted by u) number of a possible GP pair $(x, 2n - x)$.
- **Forward sieve seed** : Prime number seeds that sieve x .
- **Reverse sieve seed** : Same as forward sieve seeds, and sieve $2n - x$.
- **Seed** : Sequential arrangement of prime numbers in $3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{2n}$, required for the sieve of Eratosthenes. For example, in Table 1, $2n = 50, \sqrt{50} > 7.07$, and 7 is the greatest prime number less than or equal to 7.07.

- **Vertical arrangement.**

- All possible GPs ($x, 2n - x$) are vertically arranged.

- **Other cells.**

- **md** : If $x = mp_i$, where p_i is a seed, that cell is marked as *md*.
- **mu** : If $2n - x = mp_i$, where p_i is a seed, that cell is marked as *mu*.

In Table 1, if x or $2n - x$ is prime, it is marked as red, so, when two numbers are marked as red, it is a GP.

Definition 2.3. Seed set : Set of prime numbers in $3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{2n}$, required for the sieve of Eratosthenes, and is denoted by $S = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k\}$.

Note that, for convenience sake, $p_0 = 2$, is intentionally excluded as the first prime number.

Definition 2.4. Forward phase : The value of x where the first *1d* appears.

Forward phase is same as the seed value p_i itself, i.e., for $p_1 = 3$, it is 3, $p_2 = 5$, it is 5. Forward phase is fixed regardless of n .

Definition 2.5. Reverse phase : The value of x where the first *mu* appears, $d_{p_i} = 2n \bmod p_i$.

Reverse phase varies as n changes. In Table 1, for $p_1 = 3$ it is 2, for $p_2 = 5$ it is 5 or 0.

Definition 2.6. Forward phase set : A set of all forward phases, $D_f = \{d_{3f}, d_{5f}, \dots\}$.

Definition 2.7. Reverse phase set : A set of all reverse phases, $D_r = \{d_{3r}, d_{5r}, \dots\}$.

GPMT is a table representation of symmetry and period properties of GC, which can also be represented as sinusoidal functions introduced in the following sections.

3. Eratosthenes Sieve Functions(SFs)

The sieve of Eratosthenes is a traditional method for finding all prime numbers up to any given number. It does so by iteratively, or periodically, removing the multiples of each seed prime, as shown in Figure 1.

	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40

Figure 1. Example Eratosthenes sieve.

In Figure 1, the multiples of 2, 3 and 5 is crossed by lines. The number of crosses means how many times a number has been the multiples of prime numbers 2, 3, 5, respectively.

To functionally represent the Eratosthenes sieve, we introduce SFs and Composite SFs(CSFs).

Definition 3.1. Sieve Function(SF) : A sine function, $f_{p_i}(x) = \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{p_i}\right)$ where p_i is i 'th prime number, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Example SFs.

Figure 2 (a) is SF for $p_0 = 2$ and (b) is for $p_1 = 3$. When $x = tp_i$, $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, $f_{p_i}(x) = \sin\left(\frac{\pi tp_i}{p_i}\right) = \sin(\pi t) = 0$. Considering zeros of an SF as the sieved numbers, it is exactly same as the sieve of Eratosthenes, except when $t = 1$.

Definition 3.2. Composite Sieve Function(CSF) : A product of SFs, $F_k(x) = \prod_{i=1}^k f_{p_i}(x)$, where p_i is the i 'th prime number, as in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Example CSF, $n = 25$, $k = 3$, $S = \{3, 5, 7\}$.

Definition 3.3. Forward Sieve Function Set(FSFS) : A set, $G_f = \{f_{p_1}(x), f_{p_2}(x), \dots, f_{p_k}(x)\}$, as in Figure 4.

* $G_f = \{f_{p_1}(x), f_{p_2}(x), f_{p_3}(x)\}$

Figure 4. Example FSFS, $n = 25$.

In Figure 4, $G_f = \{\sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{3}\right), \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{5}\right), \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{7}\right)\}$, and the forward phase set is $D_f = \{3, 5, 7\} = \{0, 0, 0\}$.

Definition 3.4. Reverse Sieve Function Set(RSFS) : A set, $G_r = \{f_{p_1}(2n - x), f_{p_2}(2n - x), \dots, f_{p_k}(2n - x)\}$, as in Figure 5.

* $G_r = \{f_{p_1}(2n - x), f_{p_2}(2n - x), f_{p_3}(2n - x)\}$

Figure 5. Example RSFS, $n = 25$.

In Figure 5, $G_r = \{\sin(\frac{\pi(2n-x)}{3}), \sin(\frac{\pi(2n-x)}{5}), \sin(\frac{\pi(2n-x)}{7})\}$, and the reverse phase set is $D_r = \{2, 5, 1\} = \{2, 0, 1\}$.

Definition 3.5. Total Sieve Function Set(TSFS) : A set $G_t = \{f_{p_1}(x), f_{p_2}(x), \dots, f_{p_k}(x), f_{p_1}(2n-x), f_{p_2}(2n-x), \dots, f_{p_k}(2n-x)\}$, as in Figure 6.

$$* G_t = \{f_{p_1}(x), f_{p_2}(x), \dots, f_{p_k}(x), f_{p_1}(2n-x), f_{p_2}(2n-x), \dots, f_{p_k}(2n-x)\}$$

Figure 6. Example TSFS, $n = 25$.

In Figure 6, $G_t = \{\sin(\frac{\pi x}{3}), \sin(\frac{\pi x}{5}), \sin(\frac{\pi x}{7}), \sin(\frac{\pi(2n-x)}{3}), \sin(\frac{\pi(2n-x)}{5}), \sin(\frac{\pi(2n-x)}{7})\}$, and the phase set is $D_t = \{0, 0, 0, 2, 0, 1\}$.

4. GC False Condition

In previous sections, the symmetry and period properties of GC are visually shown, from which, if GC is false, we could induce a condition set. Figure 7 depicts the positions of all prime numbers and their symmetry values between 1 and $2n$.

Figure 7. Symmetry property of GC.

In Figure 7, the sieve set is $S = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k\}$ and the maximum left side prime number is p_m . The symmetry position of left side prime number p_i is $2n - p_i$. Right side prime number is q_j and its symmetry position is $2n - q_j$.

GPMT and SFs also comprise the above symmetry property as a table and sinusoidal functions. From the patterns of FSFS, RSFS and TSFS, we can derive the following lemma.

Lemma 4.1. If GC is false, conditions on FSFS, RSFS and TSFS in Table 2 must be satisfied.

Table 2. GC false zero or non-zero conditions.

View	Condition ID	Left side condition					Right side condition				
		1	$p_1 \sim p_k$	$p_{k+1} \sim p_m$	$2n - q_j$	compL	$2n - 1$	$2n - p_1 \sim p_k$	$2n - p_{k+1} \sim p_m$	q_j	compR
FSFS	C_f	×	○	×	○	○	dc	○	○	×	○
RSFS	C_r	dc	○	○	×	○	×	○	×	○	○
TSFS	$C_t = C_f \cup C_r$	dc	○	○	○	○	dc	○	○	○	○

* ○ : must be zero, × : must not be zero, dc : don't care, compL/R : Left/Right side composite numbers

Proof. The rationales of each conditions in Table 2 are as follows.

Table 3. Rationales of GC false zero or non-zero conditions.

View	Condition ID	Left side condition		Right side condition	
		Condition	Rationale	Condition	Rationale
FSFS	C_f	1	× no $f_{p_i}(x)$ can pass 1	2n-1	dc $f_{p_i}(x)$ can pass 2n-1
		$p_1 \sim p_k$	○ $f_{p_i}(x), 1 \leq i \leq k$ pass $p_1 \sim p_k$.	$2n-p_1 \sim p_k$	○ if $2n-p_i$ is prime GC is true
		$p_{k+1} \sim p_m$	× $p_{k+1} \sim p_m$ are prime numbers	$2n-p_{k+1} \sim p_m$	○ if $2n-p_i$ is prime GC is true
		$2n-q_j$	○ if $2n-q_j$ is prime GC is true	q_j	× q_j is a prime number
		compL	○ left side composite numbers	compR	○ right side composite numbers
RSFS	C_r	1	dc symmetry point of 2n-1	2n-1	× symmetry point of 1
		$p_1 \sim p_k$	○ symmetry point of $2n-p_1 \sim p_k$	$2n-p_1 \sim p_k$	○ symmetry point of $p_1 \sim p_k$
		$p_{k+1} \sim p_m$	○ symmetry point of $2n-p_{k+1} \sim p_m$	$2n-p_{k+1} \sim p_m$	× symmetry point of $p_{k+1} \sim p_m$
		$2n-q_j$	× symmetry point of q_j	q_j	○ symmetry point of $2n-q_j$
		compL	○ symmetry point of compR	compR	○ symmetry point of compL
TSFS	$C_t = C_f \cup C_r$	1	dc	2n-1	dc
		$p_1 \sim p_k$	○	$2n-p_1 \sim p_k$	○
		$p_{k+1} \sim p_m$	○ zeros of FSFS and RSFS	$2n-p_{k+1} \sim p_m$	○ zeros of FSFS and RSFS
		$2n-q_j$	○	q_j	○
		others	○	others	○

Table 2 is just a summary of the rationales of Table 3. So, if GC is false, conditions on FSFS, RSFS and TSFS in Table 2 must be satisfied. ■

The condition $C_t = C_f \cup C_r$ states that all numbers between 1 and $2n$, except 1, must be zeros of TSFS. If this can not be satisfied, GC is true.

Definition 4.2. GC false condition : Condition $C_t = C_f \cup C_r$, that all numbers between 1 and $2n$, except 1, must be zeros of TSFS.

5. Proof by Complementary Function Concept

Definition 5.1. Complementary SF : An SF whose zeros comprise all non-zeros of an SF.

Definition 5.2. Strong Complementary SF : An SF whose zeros are exactly the non-zeros of an SF and whose non-zeros are exactly the zeros of an SF.

(a) Complementary SF of $f_2(x)$.

(b) Complementary SF of $f_3(x)$ does not exist.

Figure 8. Graphs for complementary SF concept.

In Figure 8, $f_2(x - 1)$ is a strong complementary SF of dashed graph $f_2(x)$. But, $f_3(x - 1)$ can not be a complementary SF of dashed graph $f_3(x)$, because zeros of $f_3(x - 1)$ can not comprise all non-zeros of $f_3(x)$.

Lemma 5.3. Any SF $f_{p_i}(x)$ can not have a complementary SF except when $p_0 = 2$.

Proof. When $p_0 = 2$, $f_2(x)$ has a complementary SF $f_2(x - 1)$. But, when $p_i \geq 3$, $f_{p_i}(x - d)$, $d = 1, 2, \dots, p_i - 1$, can not be a complementary SF, because its zeros can not comprise all non-zeros of $f_{p_i}(x)$. ■

Definition 5.4. Complementary CSF : A CSF whose zeros comprise all non-zeros of a CSF.

Figure 9 shows two complementary CSFs of $f_2(x)f_3(x)$, one is $f_2(x - 1)f_3(x)$ and the other is $f_2(x - 1)f_3(x - 1)$. Dotted graphs are $f_2(x)f_3(x)$. We can see that the zeros of $f_2(x - 1)f_3(x)$ and $f_2(x - 1)f_3(x - 1)$ comprise all non-zeros of $f_2(x)f_3(x)$, because of the intervening $f_2(x - 1)$.

(a) Dotted $f_2(x)f_3(x)$ with $f_2(x - 1)f_3(x)$.

(b) Dotted $f_2(x)f_3(x)$ with $f_2(x - 1)f_3(x - 1)$.

Figure 9. Examples of complementary CSF.

Figure 10 shows a dotted CSF $f_3(x)f_5(x)$ and $f_3(x - 1)f_5(x - 2)$. We can see that zeros of $f_3(x - 1)f_5(x - 2)$ can not comprise all the odd non-zeros of $f_3(x)f_5(x)$, such as 11, 23. So, $f_3(x - 1)f_5(x - 2)$ can not be a complementary CSF of $f_3(x)f_5(x)$.

* Dotted graph is $f_3(x)f_5(x)$ and line graph is $f_3(x - 1)f_5(x - 2)$.

Figure 10. CSF with no complementary CSF.

Lemma 5.5. Complementary SF or complementary CSF must have the same period with SF or CSF.

Proof. SF and CSF are sinusoidal functions with finite period, so, will repeat their non-zeros within the first period infinitely many times. To comprise all infinitely repeating non-zeros of SF or CSF, complementary SF or complementary CSF must have the same period with SF or CSF. ■

Lemma 5.6. The product of SF with complementary SF or the product of CSF with complementary CSF must comprise all integers as its zeros.

Proof. By definition a complementary function comprises all non-zeros of SF or CSF as its zeros. So, there can not exist any non-zeros when two functions are multiplied. ■

Definition 5.7. Paired SF(PSF) : A product, $h_{p_i}(x) = f_{p_i}(x)f_{p_i}(2n - x) = f_{p_i}(x)f_{p_i}(x - d_{p_i})$, $d_{p_i} = 2n \bmod p_i$.

Note that $d_{p_i} = 0$, when $2n$ is multiple of p_i . Figures 11 (a), (b) depict, for $2n = 50$, $h_3(x) = f_3(x)f_3(50 - x) = f_3(x)f_3(x - 2)$ and $h_5(x) = f_5(x)f_5(50 - x) = f_5(x)f_5(x)$. Figures 11 (c), (d) depict $h_5(x) = f_5(x)f_5(x - 2)$ and $h_7(x) = f_7(x)f_7(x - 5)$.

Figure 11. PSF examples.

In Figure 11, we can see that PSF is also a periodic sinusoidal function with period p_i .

Lemma 5.8. A PSF can not be a complementary PSF of other PSF.

Proof. A PSF has period p_i and other PSF has period $p_j \neq p_i$. So, by lemma 5.5, a PSF can not be a complementary PSF of other PSF. ■

Lemma 5.9. The product of PSFs can not have another PSF as a complementary function.

Proof. The product of k PSPs is $H_k(x) = \prod_{i=1}^k h_{p_i} = \prod_{i=1}^k f_{p_i}(x) f_{p_i}(2n - x)$. The period of $H_k(x)$ is $\prod_{i=1}^k p_i$, which can not be same as the period of any other PSF that has the period $p_j > p_k$. So, by lemma 5.5, the product of PSFs can not have another PSF as a complementary function. ■

Lemma 5.10. The product of two CSFs $H_k(x) = \prod_{i=1}^k f_{p_i}(x) f_{p_i}(2n - x) = F_k(x)F_k(2n - x)$ can not comprise all integers between 1 and $2n$ as its zeros. So, the GC false condition C_t can not be satisfied.

Proof. By lemma 5.9, $H_{k-1}(x)$ can not have $h_k(x)$, which is a PSF, as complementary function. So, $H_k(x) = h_k(x)H_{k-1}(x)$ can not comprise all integers between 1 and $2n$ as i

ts zeros. Considering that the zeros of TSFS in lemma 4.1 are the zeros of $H_k(x)$, the GC false condition C_t can not be satisfied, proving that GC is true. ■

Corollary 5.11. A CSF $F_k(x)$ can not have $F_k(2n - x)$ as a complementary CSF.

Proof. Lemma 5.10 states that $F_k(x)F_k(2n - x)$ can not comprise all integers between 1 and $2n$ as its zeros, so, $F_k(2n - x)$ can not be a complementary CSF of $F_k(x)$. ■

6. Conclusion

In this thesis, we devised GPMT and SF to visually understand the various symmetry and period properties of GC. They have the properties of sinusoidal functions, from which we could derive the GC false condition of lemma 4.1. To show GC false condition can not be satisfied, we introduced the complementary function concept. The existence of complementary function of SF or CSF requires that the period must be same as SF or CSF itself, as in lemma 5.5. GC false condition can not be satisfied, so, GC is true.

References

- [1] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Christian_Goldbach
- [2] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goldbach%27s_conjecture
- [3] <http://sweet.ua.pt/tos/goldbach.html>
- [4] Richard K. Guy, Unsolved problems in number theory, Third Edition, Springer-Verlag, Berlin (2004).
- [5] Johan Härdig, Goldbach's Conjecture, U.U.D.M. Project Report 2020:37, Department of Mathematics Uppsala University.
- [6] H. A. Helfgott, "The Ternary Golbach Conjecture is True", arXiv:1312.7748v2 [math.NT], 17 Jan 2014.

List of Figures

1	Example Eratosthenes sieve	3
2	Example SFs	4
3	Example CSF, $n = 25$, $k = 3$, $S = \{3, 5, 7\}$	4
4	Example FSFS, $n = 25$	4
5	Example RSFS, $n = 25$	4
6	Example TSFS, $n = 25$	5
7	Symmetry property of GC	5
8	Graphs for complementary SF concept	6
9	Examples of complementary CSF	7
10	CSF with no complementary CSF	7
11	PSF examples	8

List of Tables

1	Example GPMT for $n = 25$	2
2	GC false zero or non-zero conditions	5
3	Rationales of GC false zero or non-zero conditions.....	6